

Replication Report Austin 2011

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Abstract

This report documents the replication attempt of the simulation study published in Austin, P. C. (2011). Optimal caliper widths for propensity-score matching when estimating differences in means and differences in proportions in observational studies. *Pharmaceutical Statistics*, 10(2), 150–161. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pst.433>. The study investigated the effect of varying caliper width when estimating differences in means and differences in proportions from data from observational studies using propensity-score matching. Our replication involved writing simulation code based on the information provided in the manuscript. Information provided in the original study was detailed and well structured, thus allowing us to reimplement the study to the best of our knowledge.

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1 Introduction

This replication report documents the replication attempt of the simulation study Austin, P. C. (2011). Optimal caliper widths for propensity-score matching when estimating differences in means and differences in proportions in observational studies. *Pharmaceutical Statistics*, 10(2), 150–161. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pst.433>.

The author assesses the effect of varying caliper width when estimating differences in means and differences in proportions from data from observational studies using propensity-score matching. Performance measures of interest are the reduction in bias, mean squared error as well as coverage of 95% confidence intervals. For scenarios with an effect size of zero type I error rate was additionally assessed.

Following the definition of Rougier et al. (2017) we understand the replication of a published study as writing and running new code based on the description provided in the original publication with the aim of obtaining the same results.

In addition to a computer simulation the article also presented an applied example. Due to no access to the underlying data this part of the original article will not be part of this replication.

2 Method

2.1 Information basis

The information for implementing the simulation code stemmed from the original publication which did not contain any supplemental material.

2.2 Data Generating Mechanism

Data simulation involved generating observational study data with continuous as well as binary outcomes. Information provided in the original manuscript indicated that the following simulation factors were varied in generating the artificial data.

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
<i>Varied</i>		
Outcome type	2	continuous, binary
Correlation between covariates	2	uncorrelated, pairwise correlation of 0.25
Covariate type	2	standard normal, Bernoulli random variable with parameter 0.5
Effect size	5	For binary outcomes: True risk difference = 0/ -0.02/ -0.05/ -0.10/ -0.15

Simulation factor	No. levels	Levels
		For continuous outcomes: True mean difference = 0/ 1.1/ 1.25/ 1.5/ 2
<i>Fixed</i>		
Sample size	1	n = 10000
Number of covariates	1	10
Proportion treated	1	0.25
Marginal prevalence	1	0.29
Regression coefficients for baseline covariates		see below

These simulation factors are not combined in a full-factorial way but rather comprise five scenarios. For each of these five scenarios the simulation factors outcome-type (two levels) and effect size (five levels) are systematically varied resulting in a total of 50 scenarios, each of which is run with a unique seed for 1000 repetitions.

The author refers to all but the independent normal covariates scenario as a “*sensitivity analysis*” (p. 152).

Scenario	Pairwise correlation between covariates	Covariate type
Independent normal	0	10 independent standard normal
Correlated normal	0.5	10 multivariate standard normal
Mixed 1	0	5 standard normal, 5 Bernoulli random variable with parameter 0.5
Mixed 2	0	9 Bernoulli random variable with parameter 0.5, 1 standard normal
Independent binary	0	10 Bernoulli random variable with parameter 0.5

2.2.1 Regression model for baseline covariates

Formula (1) was used to generate a treatment status for each subject by draws from a Bernoulli distribution with probability $p_{i,treat}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit}(p_{i,treat}) = & \alpha_{0,treat} + \alpha_L X_{1,i} + \alpha_L X_{2,i} + \alpha_L X_{3,i} \\ & + \alpha_M X_{4,i} + \alpha_M X_{5,i} + \alpha_M X_{6,i} \\ & + \alpha_H X_{7,i} + \alpha_H X_{8,i} + \alpha_H X_{9,i} + \alpha_{VH} X_{10,i} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with $\alpha_L = \log(1.1)$, $\alpha_M = \log(1.25)$, $\alpha_H = \log(1.5)$ and $\alpha_{VH} = \log(2)$.

For scenarios with binary outcome, outcomes were generated from a Bernoulli distribution with probability $p_{i,outcome}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit}(p_{i,outcome}) = & \alpha_{0,outcome} + \beta Z_i + \alpha_L X_{1,i} + \alpha_L X_{2,i} + \alpha_L X_{3,i} \\ & + \alpha_M X_{4,i} + \alpha_M X_{5,i} + \alpha_M X_{6,i} \\ & + \alpha_H X_{7,i} + \alpha_H X_{8,i} + \alpha_H X_{9,i} + \alpha_{VH} X_{10,i} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with $Z_i = 1$ denoting subjects exposed to the treatment and β equaling 0, 0.9077272, 0.7836084, 0.6086645 and 0.4658031 corresponding to risk differences of 0, -0.02 , -0.05 , -0.10 and -0.15 .

For scenarios with continuous outcomes, outcomes were generated according to the following regression model (3).

$$\begin{aligned} Y_i = & \alpha_{0,outcome} + \beta Z_i + \alpha_L X_{1,i} + \alpha_L X_{2,i} + \alpha_L X_{3,i} \\ & + \alpha_M X_{4,i} + \alpha_M X_{5,i} + \alpha_M X_{6,i} \\ & + \alpha_H X_{7,i} + \alpha_H X_{8,i} + \alpha_H X_{9,i} + \alpha_{VH} X_{10,i} + \varepsilon_i \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with $\alpha_{0,outcome} = 0$, $\varepsilon_i = N(0, 127.6056)$, $\alpha_L = 1.1$, $\alpha_M = 1.25$, $\alpha_H = 1.5$ and $\alpha_{VH} = 2$. β was set to 0, 1.1, 1.25, 1.5 and 2 corresponding to the respective increase in mean due to exposure to the treatment.

2.2.2 Outcome type

Data comprising two different outcome types “binary” and “continuous” were generated. These outcome types corresponded to two different effect estimates of interest “risk difference” and “mean difference”.

Binary outcome data was generated such that “the probability of the outcome would be approximately 0.29 if all subjects in the population were not exposed.” (p. 152)

2.2.3 Correlation between covariates

Most scenarios assumed covariates to be independently distributed. The “correlated normal scenario” comprised 10 covariates from a multivariate normal distribution with pairwise correlations equal to 0.25. We

implemented this by adapting the covariance matrix according to the intended correlations prior to sampling covariate data.

2.2.4 Covariate type

The scenarios “*independent normal*” as well as “*correlated normal*” comprised 10 covariates from multivariate normal distributions. The scenarios “*mixed 1*” and “*mixed 2*” comprised both independent standard normal as well as independent Bernoulli (0.5) covariates. In scenario “*mixed 1*” the first five covariates were assumed to be independent Bernoulli and in scenario “*mixed 2*” the first nine, remaining covariates were drawn from pendant standard normal distributions.

2.2.5 Effect size

For each scenario and each outcome type, data is simulated corresponding to five different effect sizes. For the binary outcome scenarios risk differences of 0, 1.1, 1.25, 1.5 and 2 were implemented. To simulate these risk differences we optimized the coefficient β i.e. the log-odds ratio relating the treatment to the outcome via binary search. This approach differs from the author, who report having used the following β s for risk differences of 0, -0.02 , -0.05 , -0.10 , -0.15 : 0, 0.9077272, 0.7836084, 0.6086645, 0.4658031.

Data generation can be summarized with the following pseudo code:

- For each of 1000 repetitions:
 - For each of 5 scenarios:
 - For each of 4 effect sizes:
 - Set unique seed (identical to repetition number)
 - Simulate observational study data
 - * Define covariance matrix corresponding to intended pairwise correlation of covariates specified by scenario at hand.
 - * Sample covariate data for 10000 cases and 10 covariates according to distributions specified in the scenario at hand.
 - * Determine $\alpha_{0,treat}$ via binary search to induce a treatment probability of 0.25.
 - * Compute linear predictor for treatment status following the regression model in (1).
 - * Sample treatment indicator Z_i from Bernoulli distribution.
 - * For binary scenarios:
 - Determine $\alpha_{0,outcome}$ via binary search to induce a marginal probability of of the event occurring in the population of 0.29.
 - Determine β via binary search to induce an ATT corresponding to the scenario at hand.
 - Obtain outcome probability for each subject
 - Sample outcome from Bernoulli distribution
 - * For continuous scenarios:
 - Sample random error ε_i for each subject from normal distribution $\varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ with $\sigma^2 = 127.6056$.)
 - Compute outcome for each subject according to (3).
 - Compute logit of propensity score for each subject
 - Obtain crude bias from unmatched sample.
 - For each caliper width γ :
 - * Get matched sample.
 - * Obtain estimates from matched sample.

2.3 Investigated Methods

The study investigates the effect of caliper width in the context of propensity score matching for estimating differences in mean (for continuous outcomes) and risk differences (for binary outcomes).

Propensity-score matching as implemented in the context of the investigated study comprised “pair-matching without replacement within a specified caliper distance [...]. Using this approach, pairs of treated and untreated subjects are formed such that the difference in propensity scores between matched subjects differs by at most a fixed distance (the caliper width). In matching without replacement, each subject can be included in at most one matched set.” (p.150)

The study “matched subjects on the logit of the propensity score using a caliper width of $\gamma\sqrt{(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2)/2}$ where σ_i^2 is the variance of the logit of the propensity score in the i th group.” (p.152) γ different propensity-score was allowed to “range from 0.05 to 2.5 in increments of 0.05. Thus, 50 matched samples were formed from each randomly generated data set.”

Due to extensive computational demands we deviated from this γ sequence and reduced the number of different caliper width to 11: 0.05, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75, 2.00, 2.25, 2.50.

2.4 Performance measures

The study investigated “the impact of caliper width on reduction in bias, mean squared error (MSE), coverage of confidence intervals, and type 1 error rates.” (p.151) For each randomly generated data set “50 different propensity-score matched samples were formed” (p.152) from the data. the treatment effect was estimated in the unmatched sample as well as in each propensity-score matched sample.

2.4.1 Within - matched pair diffence

Austin writes “Within the propensity-score matched sample, let $Y_{T,i}$ and $Y_{C,i}$ denote the outcome for the treated and untreated subjects in the i th matched set, respectively. Then let $d_i = Y_{C,i} - Y_{T,i}$ denoted the within-matched pair difference in outcome between treated and untreated subject.” We found this definition to be highly unconventional. Furthermore, this definition led to some inconsistencies. It would follow that the true treatment effect is not identical to β (see formula (2)) but rather has an opposite sign which makes code implementation unintuitive. In addition, in all figures Austin reports the “True delta” as positive thus identical to β . For reasons of convention as well as consistency and ease of implementation, we thus assumed that the above definition contained a typo. We hence assumed the effect i.e. difference in mean to refer to subtracting the outcome of the the untreated from that of the treated.

2.5 Technical implementation

The original simulation study does not specify the software environment it was implemented in. Our replication was implemented using the R programming environment (details regarding software versions can

be obtained from the section Reproducibility Information). The corresponding R code can be obtained from <https://github.com/replisims/austin2011>. The replication did not rely on any specialized packages. The following table provides an overview of replicator degrees of freedom, i.e. decisions that had to be made by the replicators because of insufficient or contradicting information. Issues were resolved by discussion among the replicators.

Issue	Replicator decision	Justification
α s not provided for mixed scenarios	α approximated by binary search.	Common practice of the replicators in their own simulation studies.
Computation time too long	Number of calipers and repetitions reduced.	Only effects resolution of results. Findings were not that fine grained.

2.6 Regression model intercepts

Intercepts for the regression models $\alpha_{0,treat}$ and $\alpha_{0,outcome}$ used for data generation that regulated treatment probability as well as the probability of the event occurring in the population if everyone were untreated were only provided for the independent normal scenario. Parameters for the other scenarios were hence obtained via binary search.

2.7 Computational cost

The present simulation required immense computational costs. The author acknowledges this as: “[i]n the independent normal covariate scenario, the use of 1,000 iterations required approximately 60 days of CPU time on a unix server.” A decade later this issue was still so severe that replicating the study with the original number of replication and caliper widths was not feasible. We hence reduced the number of replications from 1000 to 100 and the number of caliper widths from 50 to 11.

3 Results

Austin presents their results exclusively in table form separated by outcome and covariate type. The five different sizes per scenario are represented as different lines within the same panels. The following figures show the original as well as the replicated result figures side by side in the order and numbering as the original paper.

3.1 Replication of result figures

Whenever the data range allowed we adopted the same scaling as the original figures to facilitate visual comparison.

3.1.1 Reduction in bias - Figure 1

Figure 1: Caliper width and reduction in bias: risk differences. Left side: original study; right side: replication.

3.1.2 Mean squared error - Figure 2

Figure 2: Caliper width and MSE: risk difference. Left figure: original study; right figure: replication.

3.1.3 Coverage of 95% CIs - Figure 3

Figure 3: Caliper width and coverage of 95% confidence intervals: risk difference. Left figure: original study; right figure: replication.

3.1.4 Empirical type I error rate - Figure 4

Figure 4: Caliper width and Type 1 error rates. Left figure: original study; right figure: replication.

3.1.5 Reduction in bias - Figure 5

Figure 5: Caliper width and reduction in bias: differences in means. Left figure: original study; right figure: replication.

3.1.6 Mean squared error - Figure 6

Figure 6: Caliper width and reduction in bias: differences in means. Left figure: original study; right figure: replication.

3.1.7 Coverage of 95% CIs - Figure 7

Figure 7: Caliper width and reduction in bias: differences in means. Left figure: original study; right figure: replication.

4 Discussion

4.1 Replicability

The present replication attempt can be summarized as rather straight forward. With the rare exception the data generating mechanism as well as simulation parameters were well documented and the methods section well structured. Result reporting was complete allowing the comparison of performance measures across all scenarios.

4.2 Replicator degrees of freedom

However, there were some details which were undefined or counter to our experience. The values of $\alpha_{0,treat}$ and $\alpha_{0,outcome}$ were not only not provided for any scenario but the “*independent normal scenario*” their adaptation was also discussed in a rather odd place i.e. the end of the section 3.1.2. detailing the data generation of the continuous outcomes even though these parameters pertained to the data generation for binary outcomes discussed in section 3.1.1. For consistency we approximated these parameters via binary search for all scenarios even those for which they were provided by the author.

Due to the immense computational cost we had to simplify the replication attempt by reducing the number of caliper width to 22% of the number investigated in the original study. We furthermore reduced the number of replications to 10% of the original number. Despite these substantial reductions the present replication ran for the equivalence of approximately 1000 days CPU time. Such massive computational costs do not leave a lot of room for trial and error in figuring out the simulation setup.

4.3 Equivalence of results

All replicated results pertaining to binary outcomes (figures 1 -4) closely align with the original results. The only noteworthy deviation being that in our replication an increasing caliper width did not seem to decrease performance as heavily for the independent normal covariate scenarios. Despite the slight deviations all conclusions drawn by Austin in the in text result summary could also be concluded from our results. For the scenarios pertaining to continuous outcomes (figure 4-7) our findings deviate considerably from the original study. They agree in general trend, however any decrease in performance is heavily amplified and near perfect reduction of bias never reached. We attribute this to a potential bias in the data generation. Albeit intense debugging efforts we were unfortunately not able to locate the source of the potential bias. To locate potential sources of error simulation descriptives summarizing key features of the simulated data beyond the performance measures might have been helpful. Given the high number of caliper width and simulation repetitions the granularity of result figures is rather low. A detailed comparison of the results e.g. pertaining to different effect sizes is impossible as the different lines cannot be reliably distinguished let alone attributed to an effect size with the figure scaling chosen.

5 Contributions

Authors made the following contributions according to the CRediT framework <https://casrai.org/credit/>

Anna Lohmann:

- Data Curation
- Formal Analysis (lead)
- Investigation
- Software
- Visualization (lead)
- Writing - Original Draft Preparation
- Writing - Review & Editing

Rolf H. H. Groenwold :

- Formal Analysis (supporting)
- Investigation
- Software (supporting)
- Validation

References

- 1 Rougier, Nicolas P., Konrad Hinsén, Frédéric Alexandre, Thomas Arildsen, Lorena A. Barba, Fabien C. Y. Benureau, C. Titus Brown, et al. 2017. "Sustainable Computational Science: The ReScience Initiative." *PeerJ Computer Science* 3 (December): e142. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.142>.

Appendix

Simulation Code

The code and the files associated are organized in the form of a research compendium which can be found in the following git repository <https://github.com/replisims/austin2011>

Reproducibility Information

This report was last updated on 2023-01-02 14:46:08. The simulation replication was conducted using the following computational environment and dependencies:

```
## - Session info -----
## setting value
## version R version 4.1.3 (2022-03-10)
## os      Windows 10 x64 (build 19045)
## system  x86_64, mingw32
## ui      RTerm
## language (EN)
## collate English_United States.1252
## ctype   English_United States.1252
## tz      Europe/Berlin
## date    2023-01-02
## pandoc  2.18 @ C:/Program Files/RStudio/bin/quarto/bin/tools/ (via rmarkdown)
##
## - Packages -----
## package      * version   date (UTC) lib source
## assertthat   0.2.1     2019-03-21 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## cachem       1.0.6     2021-08-19 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## callr        3.7.1     2022-07-13 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## cli          3.4.1     2022-09-23 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## crayon       1.5.1     2022-03-26 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## DBI          1.1.3     2022-06-18 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## devtools     2.4.3     2021-11-30 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## digest       0.6.29    2021-12-01 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## dplyr        * 1.0.9     2022-04-28 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## ellipsis     0.3.2     2021-04-29 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## evaluate     0.15      2022-02-18 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## fansi        1.0.3     2022-03-24 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## fastmap      1.1.0     2021-01-25 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## fs           1.5.2     2021-12-08 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## generics     0.1.3     2022-07-05 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## glue         1.6.2     2022-02-24 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## here         1.0.1     2020-12-13 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## htmltools    0.5.2     2021-08-25 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## knitr        * 1.39      2022-04-26 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## lifecycle    1.0.1     2021-09-24 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## magrittr     2.0.2     2022-01-26 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## memoise      2.0.1     2021-11-26 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## pillar       1.8.0     2022-07-18 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## pkgbuild     1.3.1     2021-12-20 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## pkgconfig    2.0.3     2019-09-22 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
```

```

## pkgload          1.3.0      2022-06-27 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## prettyunits     1.1.1      2020-01-24 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## processx        3.7.0      2022-07-07 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## ps              1.6.0      2021-02-28 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## purrr           0.3.4      2020-04-17 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## R6              2.5.1      2021-08-19 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## remotes         2.4.2      2021-11-30 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## ReplisimReport  0.0.0.9000 2022-02-03 [1] Github (replisims/ReplisimReport@5f14003)
## rlang           1.0.4      2022-07-12 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## rmarkdown       2.13       2022-03-10 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## rprojroot       2.0.3      2022-04-02 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## rstudioapi      0.13       2020-11-12 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## sessioninfo     1.2.2      2021-12-06 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## stringi         1.7.8      2022-07-11 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## stringr         1.4.0      2019-02-10 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## tibble          3.1.8      2022-07-22 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## tidyselect      1.1.2      2022-02-21 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## usethis         2.1.5      2021-12-09 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## utf8            1.2.2      2021-07-24 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## vctrs           0.4.1      2022-04-13 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## xfun            0.31       2022-05-10 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.3)
## xtable          * 1.8-4     2019-04-21 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
## yaml           2.3.5      2022-02-21 [1] CRAN (R 4.1.2)
##
## [1] C:/Users/alohmann/Documents/R/win-library/4.1
## [2] C:/Program Files/R/R-4.1.3/library
##
## -----

```